

A 3D-DIC Based System for Measuring Finger Pad Displacement Distribution During Contact with Grooved Textures: A Preliminary Study

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Abstract. Detailed observation of fingertip deformation during object contact is essential for elucidating the mechanisms of human tactile perception. While transparent plates are commonly used to measure skin behavior under normal and tangential pressures with high resolution, light refraction often limits the use of textured stimuli by causing image distortion. In this paper, to mitigate distortion and occlusion caused by refraction, we constructed a transparent stimulus with grooves featuring precise vertical side walls. By integrating this with a 3D-DIC system operating at high speed, we achieved simultaneous 3D reconstruction of the finger pad areas viewed through both the groove and ridge regions of the transparent plate.

Keywords: Skin deformation · 3D-DIC · Displacement measurement · Tactile perception.

1 Introduction

Recently, several studies have been conducted to elucidate the mechanisms of human tactile perception by observing the complex mechanical behavior generated when fingertips contact objects. This research involves applying normal and tangential pressures to the fingertip using a transparent plate, and then performing high-resolution 2D and 3D measurements of the deformation using high-speed cameras and techniques such as optical flow[1], DIC(Digital Image Correlation)[2], and OCT(Optical Coherence Tomography)[3]. However, in measurements using high-speed cameras, the refraction of light through transparent objects distorts the image and creates invisible regions, making it difficult to use surfaces with fine irregularities, similar to those found in natural objects, as physical stimuli for the fingertip. On the other hand, while OCT measurements have been used to measure finger deformation in response to small protrusions, the technical difficulty of high-speed imaging prevents the measurement of rapid deformations occurring in human fingertips.

Therefore, in this paper, in order to suppress image distortion and occlusion due to refraction, we created a transparent plate with grooves that are precise vertical side walls, and applied it to a 3D-DIC system using a high-speed camera to simultaneously reconstruct both groove and ridge regions in three dimensions.

Fig. 1. (a) Transparent plate with grooved texture. (b) Measurement system setup. (c) Separate ROIs for DIC Analysis.

2 System and Experiment

As shown in Fig. 1(a), grooves were precisely cut through a 1.0 mm thick transparent acrylic plate using an end mill, ensuring that the sides were perpendicular to the plate surface. Next, as shown in Fig. 1(b), the horizontal axes of the two high-speed cameras were aligned with the long side of the groove. This minimizes the problem of the side walls of grooves creating blind spots and obstructing the object being measured.

When photographing an object through acrylic of varying thicknesses, the angle of incidence to the lens changes due to the refraction of light. This results in geometric distortion and differences in optical distance. To address this image misalignment, separate ROIs (Regions of Interest) were set for the groove and ridge regions, as shown in Fig. 1(c). By individually applying dedicated calibration data corresponding to the thickness of each region, measurement errors caused by refraction were suppressed.

The process of a participant (female, 20s) pressing her left middle finger perpendicularly against a transparent acrylic plate with a groove width of 0.5 mm was captured using stereo measurement with two high-speed cameras. The optical system consisted of a main lens with a 0.5x magnification, fitted with a teleconverter to achieve a combined magnification of 1.0x. Light from an LED light source was irradiated via a linear light guide and a diffuser to ensure the necessary brightness for high-speed imaging. The shooting frame rate was 750 fps, the image resolution was 2048×2048 pixels, and the lateral spatial resolution was approximately $10 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. The speckle pattern for measurement was formed by spraying a water-diluted purple surgical skin marker onto the fingertip with an airbrush. 3D-DIC software VIC-3D (Correlated Solutions) was used for analysis. The moment the fingertip lightly touched the transparent plate was defined as the reference image (initial state), and the three-dimensional displacement distribution was calculated by setting the subset size in the analysis to a 31-pixel square.

Fig. 2. Three dimensional displacement distribution in the depth direction (W component) for a fingertip: (a) initial state defined as the reference showing zero displacement, and (b) state after slight indentation relative to (a).

3 Result and Discussion

Fig. 2 shows the distribution of displacement in the depth direction (W component) when a fingertip is pressed against a grooved transparent plate. The measurement results demonstrated that simultaneous three dimensional reconstruction of the finger pad areas, viewed through both the concave and convex regions, can be achieved over approximately half of the contact surface.

Future challenges include measuring the movement of the fingertip as it traces over the grooves. In this case, it will be necessary to adapt the analysis algorithm to address data discontinuities that occur when subsets cross the boundaries of the grooves. Furthermore, it is essential to conduct a quantitative accuracy evaluation of this system to ensure the validity of the obtained data.

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

The high-precision deformation data obtained with this measurement system will directly contribute to refining finite element (FE) models of fingertips and predicting the responses of tactile receptors. In the future, we plan to develop interdisciplinary discussions linking physical deformation and perceptual mechanisms through collaborative research with biomechanics researchers using FEM and neurophysiologists of touch.

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References

1. Levesque, V., Hayward, V.: Experimental evidence of lateral skin strain during tactile exploration. In: Proc. Eurohaptics 2003, pp. 261–275. Dublin, Ireland (2003)
2. Doumont, D., Kao, A., Lambert, J., Wielant, F., Gerling, G., Delhayé, B., Lefèvre, P.: 3-D Reconstruction of Fingertip Deformation During Contact Initiation. *Multi-sens. Res.* **39**(3-5), 325–350 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134808-bja10168>
3. Corniani, G., Lee, Z.S., Carré, M.J., Lewis, R., Delhayé, B.P., Saal, H.P.: Sub-surface deformation of individual fingerprint ridges during tactile interactions. *eLife* **13**, RP93554 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.93554.2>